

Requirements for Completion of the Integration Phase

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Disclaimer:

This document refers to the status of Base4NFDI's developments in September 2025. Many aspects are still under discussion, particularly with regard to the scope and functionalities of the upcoming NFDI service portfolio (discussions only started in spring 2025), which will affect workflows and responsibilities. Any adjustments to these will be addressed in revised versions of this document.

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1. Purpose

This document serves as a **common framework** for the Integration Phase of your basic service. It applies to all basic services and their proposals as of September 2025 and later.

There are **six mandatory deliverables** from Task Area 2 (Base4NFDI) and **three conditionally required ones**. All deliverables and their results must be documented in the Base4NFDI project management software OpenProject. TA2 will generate the corresponding work packages and templates for the basic services.

Please utilise the support offered by the Base4NFDI team (TA2, Service Stewards) if you encounter any difficulties. Also remember that you might have to prepare your next basic service **proposal for the Ramp-Up Phase** in the second half of the Integration Phase, for which you need an up-to-date state of a few of these deliverables. These measurable interim results can contribute to a successful follow-up application.

2. Scope of integration

“Service integration” addresses different but interdependent developments of both the service teams and Task Area 2 of Base4NFDI:

- The **service teams** take the service from the prototypical state it reached in the Initialisation Phase to a fully developed and functional one in the Integration Phase. The steps for this are described in the work programme of the integration proposal, and the concrete objectives are defined by corresponding own service-specific deliverables and milestones.
- **Base4NFDI** is developing the framework, the service lifecycle management, and procedures of the future service portfolio of the NFDI, as described in the Base4NFDI proposal.¹

Base4NFDI supports the service teams in building their services in such a way that they not only fit into the service landscape of the NFDI in a coherent and quality-assured manner, but are also interoperable in a wider context, e. g., the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC).

As their first priority, the service team is advised to focus on their work plan and achieve their own Integration Phase objectives described therein. Secondly, based on these achievements, the team is asked to document their success in developing the service, the success of the service itself, and its quality, maturity, and sustainability. Base4NFDI supports the team with appropriate templates and guidelines and helps mapping the team's individual deliverables to the overarching objectives of Base4NFDI itself. Finally,

¹ Bernard, L., Altenhöner, R., Böhm, F., Diepenbroek, M., Ebert, B., Fluck, J., Herres-Pawlis, S., Klinger, A., Koepler, O., Lorenz, S., Mathiak, B., Miller, B., Pelz, P., Reißler-Pipka, N., Ritz, R., Sax, U., Schimmler, S., Schörner, T., Schrade, T., ... Suchodoletz, D. von . (2023). Base4NFDI - Basic Services for NFDI. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10245518>

Base4NFDI will formally sign off on the fulfilment of the Integration Phase deliverables. At this point, the service team is asked to announce the completion of the Integration Phase, at least by a contribution to the Base4NFDI newsletter and website and a presentation of the results in a meeting of their respective section. This marks the successful completion of the Integration Phase.

3. Timeline

The following figure represents what is to be done by **Base4NFDI** (beige) and **service teams** (green) during the Integration Phase. The service team's own workplan, tasks, and deliverables mark the starting and pivotal point of these activities. This is mapped to the Integration Phase deliverables D.Int.1–6 as indicated in Figure 1 and explained individually below. Fulfilment of these deliverables is tracked by respective OpenProject tasks. We strongly recommend to regularly use OpenProject during the course of the Integration Phase for the documentation of results as they become available.

Figure 1. Scheme of a service team's (green) and Base4NFDI's (beige) collaboration in Integration Phase

All requirements shown above are due at the **end of the Integration Phase** with the following exceptions:

1. There must be an **initial meeting on usability study until month 3** and, if applicable, a usability study plan until month 5.
2. If applicable, there must be a **software self-assessment by month 18**.
3. **Parts of the service metadata** will be needed **by month 18** for the **ramp-up proposal**.

Please mind that, analogous to the Initialisation Phase, an **interim report** for the ramp-up proposal will be necessary. This should report the current state of and planned next steps regarding service quality, maturity, and sustainability. Therefore, the team is asked to provide this information in the corresponding OP work packages of D.Int.1 and D.Int.2 and attach it to the proposal.

The following **Table 1** illustrates the timeline of the Integration Phase, along with regular tasks mentioned at the bottom.

Due until	Task	Responsibilities
Before applying for integration	Meeting with TA2: integration overview and respective responsibilities of service team and Base4NFDI, check of applicability of tasks D.Int.5-7	TA2: presentation SERs: coordination
Month 1	Integration kick-off workshop with Base4NFDI (TA2, service stewards, representatives of TA3 and TA4)	TA2: presentation SERs: coordination
Month 1-3	Initial meeting to discuss a strategy concerning usability, including a user study focusing on usability and user experience.	service team: provision of information TA2: consultation on planning and study design
Month 3-5	Study plan of user study (if applicable)	TA2: provide the service with study design
Before month 24	Execution of an user study (if applicable)	service team: provision of study subjects TA2: conduct study and write report

Due until	Task	Responsibilities
Month 17–18	If software is developed for the service: 1st self-assessment of software quality	service team: fill in questionnaire TA2: provide questionnaire and write report
Month 17–18	Preparation of interim reports on adoption, interoperability, success stories, quality, sustainability, technological readiness in OpenProject Application for Ramp-Up Phase	service team
Month 22–23	Preparation of final reports on adoption, interoperability, success stories, quality, sustainability, technological readiness	service team
Month 23–24	If software is developed for the service: 2nd self-assessment of software quality – update of 1st assessment if this has revealed shortcomings	service team: fill in questionnaire TA2: provide questionnaire and write report
Month 23–24	Check of fulfilment of portfolio-relevant requirements	TA2
After month 24	Confirmation of successful completion of the Integration Phase, based on the reports/checks, and final report	TA2, TA3
After month 24	Announcement of the successful completion of the Integration Phase	Base4NFDI, service team
Monthly	Jour fixe with TA1 and TA2, service stewards, other teams	
As needed	Team meetings with TA2	
Regularly	Contribution to the Base4NFDI service roadshows and similar formats	
Yearly	Base4NFDI User Conference	

Table 2 below maps the deliverables described in this document to the timeline explained above.

Deliverable Milestone	Type	Description	Due until
D.Int.1	OpenProject tables	Report on service integration and success	18M 24M
D.Int.2	OpenProject table	Service maturity report	18M 24M
D.Int.3	OpenProject table	Documentation of sustainability	24M
D.Int.4	OpenProject + Google table	Provision of service portfolio metadata	18M 24M
D.Int.5	OpenProject + Google form	Self-assessments of software quality	18M 24M
D.Int.6	OpenProject + Report by TA2	Documentation of usability	5M
D.Int.7	OpenProject	Provision of training material	24M
D.Int.8	Presentation and report	Short overview about the outcomes of the Integration Phase and presentation in a section meeting	After 24M
D.Int.9	Presentations	Talks at Base4NFDI User Conference, the Services Roadshow and a NFDITalk	As appropriate

4. Mandatory service-related deliverables

The following **four** deliverables from Task Area 2 (Base4NFDI) are mandatory for all service teams to complete the Integration Phase. We suggest making sure that you have taken all these deliverables and milestones into account when writing your proposal work plan, and/or map your own deliverables and milestones to them.

For each deliverable, TA2 will create a corresponding reporting task in the OpenProject workspace of the respective service team where a suggested structure along with further instructions can be found. Both publicly available and internal documents can be provided there as a link or as text, if necessary. An export of your documentation in OpenProject is then sufficient as a report of finalisation of the Integration Phase.

Deliverable D.Int.1 Documentation of service integration and success

During the Integration Phase, the service shall mature into an "integrated" one, which for reasons of practicability is defined as: The **integrated service**

1. has been **adopted for use by NFDI**
2. and is **interoperable with other services.**

This relates directly to the objectives the service team has laid out in their work plan for integration:

Adoption essentially means that a service is employed and utilised by individuals, communities, or consortia because it:

- provides added value to the users,
- closes thematic, methodological, or functional gaps which previously prevented effective work,
- creates new opportunities,
- expands or enhances existing possibilities,
- simplifies, streamlines, or harmonises existing methods, workflows, or access to resources that have been in place before

for

- better scientific research,
- more efficient data analysis and management,
- easier archival and dissemination of results,
- improved sharing of data, methods, concepts, and FAIR data outputs

An **interoperable** service adheres to and utilises context-relevant open standards. Depending on its given context and purpose, this can apply to four dimensions of interoperability:

- technical: application interfaces, transfer protocols,
- semantic: metadata standards, terminologies, identifier systems,
- operational: methods, workflows, best practices,
- legal: GDPR, data protection, accessibility, access regulations, service/data security.

In addition, and due to the nature of Base4NFDI itself, each service can address different **scopes of interoperability**:

- internal: a service is built to harmonise already existing services of the consortia,
- external: a service targets other entities like previously unrelated consortia, NFDI, or EOSC.

The team should document individual contributions of their achievements towards adoption and interoperability in tabular form in the OpenProject task assigned to this deliverable.

For a comprehensive summary of overall success, the service team must provide **at least two success stories**: one related to the use cases of consortia, institutions, or working groups involved in the construction of the service, and one related to use cases of other entities that have not been involved so far, to show that the service has been built fit for purpose and that it is suitable for other contexts as well, respectively. These stories should be based on actual, practical experience and refer to:

- achievements with NFDI consortia, communities, and service providers,
- specific use cases as described in the integration proposal,
- concrete improvements based on user studies,
- outcomes of incubator projects or use cases.

The **success stories** should focus on:

- added value and benefits for research,
- service adoption and usage in consortia and communities,
- integration with existing NFDI services and resources,
- interoperability with standards used in the NFDI and internationally,
- collaborations with other Basic Services,
- incubator projects.

Not every of the aspects above will be relevant for a particular service. But every Base4NFDI service is being built around objectives like those listed above, making the goals from the work plan the starting points for plausibly documenting adoption, interoperability, and success.

Documentation:

- For the documentation of results, three tables have been prepared in the OpenProject task assigned to this deliverable.
- In the first table, the team should list their own deliverables with respect to the objectives of the integration work plan and indicate if they are relevant for adoption and/or interoperability.
- In the other two tables, the team must summarise the two success stories, focusing on the minimum information requested according to the **template table 3** below.
- Using these tables is sufficient for fulfilling this requirement, but the service team is free to choose other formats and/or to include individual success stories to the OpenProject task.

Topic	Focus/scope
Basic Service	Name of the integrated service (component)
Collaboration partners such as consortia, communities, services	Names of the NFDI consortia, communities, and services involved in or addressed by the specific use case of this success story

Challenges	Short description of the challenges or requirements the involved consortia faced and which the service is intended to address
Approach	Short description of the approach and solution
Results	Concrete benefits and improvements for the involved consortia, according to the results of the project; links and references to deployments and documentation
Timeframe	Duration of the project
Involved (optional)	List of key persons or teams
Lessons learned (optional)	Important learnings from the process, either for the context of Bas4NFDI, the consortia, or other projects
Next steps (optional)	Planned further developments or adaptations

Support by Base4NFDI:

- TA2 will support the teams by identifying possible service-related topics for these reports and contextual interpretation of the different adoption and interoperability aspects. Especially with regard to interoperability with EOSC, we encourage teams to take advantage of a corresponding consultation with Base4NFDI. The service stewards can help to identify potential incubators and support the execution of incubator cycles.

Due date: The success stories are due at the end of the Integration Phase, and an interim report will be needed for the application for ramp-up.

TA2 will review and confirm the results in terms of content and plausibility, together with the service stewards if necessary, while TA3 will do the same in terms of completeness. An export of the OpenProject task will formally document the integration and success of the service.

Deliverable D.Int.2 Documentation of service maturity

The Base4NFDI proposal lists two measures to ensure an adequate quality and sustainability of a service: Firstly, and topic of this deliverable, the service should move from a technology readiness level² (TRL) of 5–6 at the end of the Initialisation Phase to TRL 7–8 at the end of the Integration Phase. Secondly, and if applicable, appropriate studies must be carried out that look at the service or software quality, its usability, and the

²

https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/wp/2014_2015/annexes/h2020-wp1415-annex-ga_en.pdf (p. 29)

extent to which it meets the needs of users. (These studies may not apply to every service and are addressed by D.Int.5 and D.Int.6 below.)

Even if a service is only partially – if at all – a technical one, the team is advised to use the **TRL concept** to document that the service has been developed accordingly. In a general sense, TRL 5–6 can be attributed to a prototype that provides essential components and has been tested by a small number of users in a limited environment. TRL 7-8 would then apply to a fully implemented service that is regularly utilised in the actually intended environment. (Further development towards a fully-fledged scale-out and long-term implementation is left for the subsequent Ramp-Up Phase.)

These definitions can be applied to any type of service and their fulfilment may be checked according to the concrete service-specific tasks and deliverables. The team must plausibly demonstrate that the service has achieved an appropriate level at the end of the Integration Phase.

Documentation:

- Based on their planned service development goals from their work plan, the team must provide keyword evidence to demonstrate that the service has reached the necessary maturity. To this end, there is a prepared table in the OpenProject task of this deliverable, asking the team to break their goals down in service characteristics related to service maturity and describe its status at the beginning and end of the Integration Phase.

Support by Base4NFDI:

- TA2 will aid the team in applying the TRL concept to their specific context and to identify the relevant, applicable concepts in their work programme.
- The related OpenProject task indicates possible interpretations/translations of the TRLs for non-technical services focusing on consulting, information, methods, and training. More information can be found on Zenodo³ and can be provided by TA2.

Due date: The final report is due at the end of the Integration Phase, and an interim report will be needed for the application for ramp-up.

TA2 will review and confirm the results in terms of content and plausibility, together with the service stewards if necessary, while TA3 will do the same in terms of completeness. An export of the OpenProject task will formally document the maturity of the service.

Deliverable D.Int.3 Documentation of sustainability

The long-term operation of the service will be fully addressed in the Ramp-Up Phase, but a clear perspective for this should already be developed in the Integration Phase. This includes (i) commissioning the organisation(s) that will operate the service and (ii)

³ Report on Base4NFDI service integration procedures: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15235863>

drafting an operational concept that sets out the required human and infrastructural resources, the foreseeable increase in requirements and information on which organisations will provide the resources. (Based on this, the actual business model is developed in the Ramp-Up Phase with details of the business form and financing.)

Documentation:

- The general provider information (imprint of hosting institution, service owner and manager, geographic location) is as well required for operating the service portfolio as detailed in deliverable D.Int.4. To avoid duplicate work, check and follow the instructions given there.
- No detailed operating concept is required. It is sufficient to compile the expected technical, personnel, and financial resources required in the table prepared in the OpenProject task of this deliverable.

Support by Base4NFDI:

- To facilitate the development of a business model in the Ramp-Up Phase, TA2 will provide a set of templates and guides that are targeted to different, typically to be expected technical and non-technical service contexts.

Due date: The provider information will be needed for the ramp-up application and must be present by month 18 of the Integration Phase, the operation concept draft / list of required resources is due at the end of the Integration Phase.

TA2 will review and confirm the results in terms of content and plausibility, together with the service stewards if necessary, while TA3 will do the same in terms of completeness. An export of the OpenProject task will formally document the anticipated sustainability of the service.

Deliverable D.Int.4 Provision of service portfolio metadata

Regardless of what form the future NFDI portfolio will take, the services must meet a common set of metadata. Otherwise, the portfolio cannot be operated effectively and consistently. This results in a set of portfolio-related requirements to be fulfilled during the Integration Phase. Most of these are descriptive and, according to experience with most service teams, almost all are already addressed in their respective initialisation and integration work plans.

All requirements are listed in an accompanying document on Zenodo⁴. Please mind that there are some more complex descriptions that will have to be provided, especially with regard to

- the capabilities and limitations of the service, (if applicable, service level agreements),

⁴ See “Notes on portfolio requirements”, published jointly with this guide, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17107044>

- a suitable set of key performance indicators. These will be important for the productive phase of the service, but as they are closely related to various aspects of service adoption, it is advisable to consider them in the Integration Phase.

Please keep the metadata short and mind as well that parts of the information will be presented to potential users of the service.

Documentation:

- Together with the service stewards and TA2 staff, the team must enter all required information in a prepared Google table which is linked to the OpenProject task of this deliverable.
- Most information will have to be given directly in this table and should therefore be concise, comprehensible, and plausible with respect to the context of the service.
- For some topics like service categories and KPIs⁵, the table provides drop-down menus to choose from.

Support by Base4NFDI:

- TA2 and the service stewards will help to map and abstract the results of the teams to the portfolio-relevant metadata. They will help record all required information.

Due date: Most metadata and descriptions are due at the end of the Integration Phase, but should be entered in the table as soon as they become available. There are some exceptions that are requested for the ramp-up proposal:

- Service provider
- Service owner/manager
- Support contact

TA2 will review and confirm the results in terms of content and plausibility, together with the service stewards if necessary, while TA3 will do the same in terms of completeness. An export of the OpenProject task will formally document that all portfolio-relevant information has been given.

5. Mandatory – if applicable – service-related deliverables

The following **three** deliverables from Task Area 2 (Base4NFDI) are mandatory for all service teams to complete the Integration Phase, if they are applicable to their service. This will be discussed and assessed in the pre-proposal consultation with TA2. We suggest making sure that you have taken all these deliverables and milestones into account when writing your proposal work plan, and/or map your own deliverables and milestones to them.

⁵ See “Notes on KPIs”, published jointly with this guide, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17107044>

Deliverable D.Int.5 Self-assessments of software quality

To ensure high software quality, the service teams are asked to go through a procedure of self-assessment three times: first, when applying for the Ramp-Up Phase, second, when finishing the Integration Phase, and third, when finishing the Ramp-Up Phase. It is always the same form that needs to be filled in, so effectively, the second and third times are updates to the initial response. Scope of the assessment is code that the teams develop themselves, not the dependencies that are out of control anyway. Projects that do not develop code at all should get in touch with TA2 to figure out what might be in scope here nevertheless.

Documentation:

- Teams will be asked to provide their assessment results through a form provided by TA2. This form covers the topics outlined in D2.1.1 (Integration procedures)⁶ and the attached “Notes on software quality”⁷.
- The completion of this must be documented in the associated OpenProject task.

Support by Base4NFDI:

- TA2 provides a checklist of relevant quality criteria the service teams are asked to fill in. The checklist can be found under the references given above.
- TA2 will help figuring out which parts of the assessment are relevant.

Due dates: The results of the first software quality assessment will be requested for the ramp-up proposal. The second software assessment is due towards the end of the Integration Phase. The third and last assessment will be due at the end of the Ramp-Up Phase.

TA2 will review and confirm the results in terms of content and plausibility, together with the service stewards if necessary, while TA3 will do the same in terms of completeness. An export of the OpenProject task will formally document the adequate quality of the software.

Deliverable D.Int.6 Documentation of usability

To ensure the usability and accessibility of the service, user studies are planned during the first five months of the Integration Phase. The user studies will be carried out by TA2 based on availability and team requirement, and the service teams are only required to have a supporting role. The primary objective is to validate the effectiveness and intuitiveness of the user interface, identify friction points, and incorporate direct feedback from representative end users. The user studies are optional but strongly encouraged to ensure the usability and accessibility of the services. TA2 will provide a necessary briefing during the initial stage of the integration to inform the service teams of the goal and

⁶ Report on Base4NFDI service integration procedures: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15235863>

⁷ See “Notes on software quality”, published jointly with this guide, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17107044>

purpose of the user studies. If the service team decides that the user study is not necessary, it is possible to opt out after the briefing with TA2.

The service team is expected to perform the following functions in order to support the user studies:

1. Provide access to the software or website to be tested,
2. Schedule an initial briefing session with TA2 to introduce the functionalities of the software or website to be tested, where TA2 will inform the team in more detail about the aim and the procedures of the study,
3. Provide contact to users of the software or website to be tested,
4. Provide follow-up support for TA2 during the user studies regarding the software or website to be tested.

Documentation:

- There will be no specific form to fill in. TA2 will provide a final report for each user study conducted for each service and link it to the OpenProject task of this deliverable.

Support by Base4NFDI:

- TA2 provides a structured report documenting the user study process and outcomes, including sections for methodology, participant demographics, key findings, usability issues, and improvement actions.
- TA2 can also provide a post-study briefing session to detail and explain the findings from the user study if required by service teams.
- Detailed information on the requested usability standards is provided in an accompanying document on Zenodo.⁸
- To ensure that usability work contributes effectively to the integration process, TA2 coordinates with service stewards and other stakeholders to align study outcomes with the broader portfolio and quality assurance requirements, as well as the needs of each service.

Due dates: Services are expected to schedule an initial meeting with TA2 within the first three months of the Integration Phase. TA2 will analyse the current state of the products and provide an analysis plan in the following months. The user study is expected to be planned within the first five months and conducted until the end of the Integration Phase.

Deliverable D.Int.7 User-centred documentation and training

User-centered documentation and training is an essential foundation for user adoption of any service. While in the Initialisation Phase, target groups and their training needs are identified and a training concept is created, in Integration Phase the focus is on

- The curation or creation of training material
- Creating and testing of documentation

⁸ See “Notes on usability”, published jointly with this guide, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17107044>

- Piloting training sessions / train the trainer programs
- Making a decision where and how to publish training material for the service
- Preparing the training work package for Ramp-Up Phase

The activities listed here should be considered when planning the Integration Phase but can be adapted to the services training needs as required.

Training activities should be considered mandatory – if applicable. In rare cases, a service might not require training activities.

Documentation:

- Open Educational Resources are tracked in the respective reporting sheet of Base4NFDI.
- Educational Events are tracked in the respective reporting sheet of Base4NFDI.
- Deliverables for training and documentation are to be mapped / added in the OpenProject task of D.Int.7 as applicable. There is no extra report for training necessary besides the own deliverables planned by the service as part of their work programme.

Support by Base4NFDI:

- The training task force, consisting of one or more service team members, the services Service Steward and the Base4NFDI Training Manager is scheduled regularly based on service needs (e.g. every 4-6 weeks). This is highly recommended and has proven valuable for teams in all phases.
- The Base4NFDI Training Manager coordinates training activities, provides feedback and quality assurance and assists planning and effort estimations. They also provide knowledge transfer and consulting and identify best practices and synergies across services and with other RDM initiatives.
- Service Stewards assist with their domain-specific knowledge and by facilitating collaboration with (future) users across NFDI consortia.

Due date: The training documentation is due at the end of the Integration Phase.

TA4 will review and confirm the results in terms of content and plausibility, while TA3 will do the same in terms of completeness. An export of the OpenProject task will formally document the integration and success of the service.

6. Mandatory presentation of results

Deliverable D.Int.8 Short overview and presentation

At the end of the Integration Phase, a short overview of the service and the results of the Integration Phase must be written. The text should include a brief overview of the service development. Possible questions to ask could be:

- What progress has been made with respect to the capabilities of the service?
- Are there additional groups of users of the service and from which thematic contexts?
- What were the prominent results of any incubator projects?

This short report will be published as a news item on the Base4NFDI website. Alternatively, you can choose your own way of publishing a summary of your basic service. In addition, there must be a presentation of the Integration Phase results in a meeting of your respective section after the phase has ended.

Documentation:

- Both the report and the presentation should be documented (e. g., linked) in the OpenProject task of this deliverable.

Due date: The report should be submitted to the Base4NFDI office and TA3 no later than **6 weeks after the end of the Integration Phase.**

If you publish your reports, please follow the [Base4NFDI publication policy](#) and the [Signalisation instructions Base4NFDI](#), and acknowledge both Base4NFDI and the funder DFG together with the funding number for basic services 521453681. It is also possible to use the Base4NFDI and DFG logos, which are available for download on this [website](#).

Deliverable D.Int.9 Participation in Base4NFDI outreach events

Active participation with a presentation of the service

- at the Base4NFDI User Conference
- at the Base4NFDI Services Roadshow
- and as a NFDI talk

is mandatory during the Integration Phase.

Documentation:

- All presentations should be listed and linked in the OpenProject task of this deliverable.

Due date: The OpenProject list should be up to date at the end of the Integration Phase.

Acknowledgements

Many of these concepts have been inspired by what HIFIS⁹ (Helmholtz Federated IT Services) has built up in recent years to bring services together in a standardised catalogue and manage them jointly. We would like to thank the HIFIS team for many fruitful and committed discussions.

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⁹ <https://hifis.net>